

ANALYSIS OF PUBLIC SERVICE QUALITY FOR VULNERABLE GROUPS AT THE INVESTMENT AND ONE-STOP INTEGRATED SERVICES OFFICE OF BALIKPAPAN CITY, EAST KALIMANTAN

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Abstract

This study aims to analyze the implementation of public services for vulnerable groups at the Balikpapan City Investment and One-Stop Integrated Services Agency (DPMPTSP). Vulnerable groups include people with disabilities, the elderly, pregnant women, and low-income communities, who often face various obstacles in accessing public services. This study used a qualitative approach with descriptive-analytical methods. Data collection was conducted through in-depth interviews with DPMPTSP officers, vulnerable groups, and relevant stakeholders, direct observation of the service process, and analysis of documents related to public service policies. The results indicate that the Balikpapan City DPMPTSP has implemented several service innovations, such as priority counters and online services, to facilitate vulnerable groups. However, several obstacles remain, such as limited human resources who understand the special needs of vulnerable groups, infrastructure that is not yet fully disability-friendly, and a digital divide that impacts access to online services. This study recommends increasing human resource capacity through sensitivity training for vulnerable groups, improvements to physical and digital infrastructure, and collaboration with community organizations to ensure inclusive and equitable public services. Implementing these recommendations is expected to improve the quality of public services and ensure that vulnerable groups' rights to access public services are fulfilled.

Keywords: *DPMPTSP, Vulnerable Groups, Public Services.*

INTRODUCTION

Public services are clearly regulated in Law No. 25 of 2009 on Public Services, which aims to provide legal certainty between the community as service recipients and service providers. Service standards serve as key benchmarks to ensure that services are delivered with quality, speed, accessibility, affordability, and measurability (Anshari, 2023). This implementation also involves leaders and persons in charge to ensure proper coordination and evaluation in order to support smooth service delivery to the public. Public service beneficiaries who continue to face challenges include vulnerable groups—individuals with physical, economic, social, or psychological limitations that hinder optimal access to public services (Salman, 2020). Many public service facilities remain insufficiently accommodating, and information on service rights and procedures is often inaccessible due to overly technical language and non-inclusive media (Subroto & Setiawan, 2024).

To address these issues, the government emphasizes the One-Stop Integrated Service (PTSP) policy, a strategic effort to simplify, accelerate, and improve service quality by integrating various licensing and non-licensing services in a single system (Gati, 2022), supported by regulations such as Presidential Regulation No. 97/2014 on the OSS system. PTSP operations are carried out by the Investment and One-Stop Integrated Services Office (DPMPTSP), responsible for providing integrated services and ensuring equitable, accessible, and inclusive services for vulnerable groups (Maysara & Asari, 2021; Rahayu et al., 2021). Priority services are offered for persons with disabilities, the elderly, and pregnant or breastfeeding women (Purnamawati et al., 2022). Balikpapan City has shown commitment through initiatives such as establishing the Public Service Mall (MPP), though challenges remain in meeting the specific needs of vulnerable groups. Local government agencies must ensure accessibility for all

disability types, guided by East Kalimantan Governor Regulation No. 22/2022, which reinforces Article 43(2) of Regional Regulation No. 1/2018 on the protection and fulfillment of the rights of persons with disabilities. DPMPTSP Balikpapan is committed to providing inclusive public services for vulnerable groups, including persons with disabilities, the elderly, pregnant women, and others requiring special attention. Priority services, special queues, and assistance are provided to ease access to licensing and non-licensing services. However, several obstacles remain. Office facilities are not fully disability-friendly, with limited ramps, accessible toilets, and adequate waiting areas—insufficient given the number of vulnerable service users. Service information often uses technical language, and inclusive formats such as braille, audio guides, or sign language are lacking. Although online services exist, many vulnerable individuals have limited access to digital technology.

There is also no formal government-provided assistance system for persons with disabilities or the elderly during licensing processes, causing prolonged administrative procedures, risks of errors, misunderstandings of requirements, and potential indirect discrimination due to unequal access. Visually, the green cluster highlights public service, service quality, effectiveness, and low-income communities. The orange cluster emphasizes vulnerable groups, public service implementation, and timeliness. The close relationship among keywords indicates that public service delivery is strongly connected to vulnerable groups, particularly in terms of implementation, timeliness, and service quality, underscoring the need for further research.

The findings of Indriani (2025) show that vulnerable groups receiving public services in libraries benefit from inclusive innovations such as accessible facilities, sign language training for staff, and mobile literacy outreach programs. Rosdiana (2020) emphasizes service provision for vulnerable and low-income groups, focusing on both service and non-service sectors, including public facilities such as roads, markets, and transportation, delivered based on efficiency and productivity. Beta Nuke Devine et al. (2024) highlight effective, structured communication between DISKOMINFO Badung and the MBM Foundation to manage complaints from vulnerable groups, stressing the need for continuous evaluation. Finally, Junriana & Faiza (2022) note that the effectiveness of services for vulnerable groups also depends on equipment conditions and stable networks.

The various foundations put forward by the researcher determine the academic gap in this study, where the researcher realizes that the research to be conducted is not solely related to public services. This research presents significant novelty in the treasury of public service quality studies, particularly those focused on vulnerable groups. Unlike previous research that has examined similar aspects in other sectors or contexts, this study offers a specific and integrated analytical lens to capture the dynamics of service within the Balikpapan City Investment and One-Stop Integrated Service Office (DPMPTSP). To understand the root of the problem and opportunities for improvement, this study goes beyond measuring quality but also explores the fundamental factors that influence it through Moenir's perspective.

METHOD

Research Approach and Type

Qualitative research emphasizes exploring various meanings to understand individuals or groups related to social problems (Sugiyono, 2020). The method used is a case study. According to Creswell (2014), case study research is a qualitative approach that explores real-life, contemporary, limited systems (cases) or multiple limited systems, through detailed and in-depth data collection involving multiple or multiple sources of information. Based on the above definition, it can be concluded that qualitative case study research is a method used to explore and understand real-life situations in detail and comprehensively. In the context of public services for vulnerable groups, this research explores the processes, perceptions, and experiences of these groups in accessing services. Qualitative research using a case study approach in public services and vulnerable groups aims to understand in-depth how public services are provided to groups in society that require special attention, such as people with disabilities, the elderly, pregnant women, and children, as well as the challenges and solutions in fulfilling their rights to fair and inclusive public services.

Data Collection Techniques

1. Interviews

A series of question-and-answer sessions between research participants and researchers is called an interview. To obtain additional information about their research subjects, researchers interview people. Interviews come in two forms: structured and unstructured. Questions are asked in systematic interviews. In contrast, limited interviews are more relaxed and informal (Moleong, 2017). This study used structured interviews in accordance with interview guidelines prepared by the researcher.

2. Documentation

Documentation is a record of past events. It can take the form of images, writings, or a person's phenomenal works. The results of interview research will be more reliable if supported by other data, such as documentation. Researchers use documentation studies to complement the data being studied. This documentation study aims to refine and complete the data obtained from interviews and observations.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Based on the results of the research conducted, the researcher presents the dialectic between theory and findings as follows:

Public Service Quality for Vulnerable Groups at DPMPTSP Balikpapan City

1. Tangibles

The quality of public services for vulnerable groups at the Investment and One-Stop Integrated Services Office (DPMPTSP) of Balikpapan City shows significant efforts in meeting basic needs through the provision of several accessibility-supporting facilities; however, notable shortcomings remain. Some facilities meet the basic needs of vulnerable groups such as the elderly, persons with disabilities, and pregnant women, yet many essential elements are still not optimally available or entirely absent. One major challenge is the lack of adequate communication aids, such as hearing support systems, interactive communication boards, or sign language interpreters, which hinders communication for individuals with hearing or speech disabilities.

In addition, the available consultation rooms do not guarantee the privacy and comfort required, especially for discussing sensitive personal matters, thereby reducing trust and participation during service processes. Accessibility to transportation for vulnerable groups is also still very limited, as there are no special transport vehicles, disability-friendly road conditions, or adequate ramps and sidewalks, making travel to the service location risky and exhausting.

To achieve truly inclusive service, strategic steps are needed, such as establishing private consultation rooms, providing staff training on empathy and social justice, and collaborating with public or special transportation services for vulnerable groups (Novita et al., 2024). With firm and sustainable efforts, DPMPTSP Balikpapan has strong potential to become a model of fair, humane, and sustainable public service for all citizens, especially the most vulnerable.

The quality of public service at DPMPTSP Balikpapan can be evaluated using the Public Service Standards framework, which includes timeliness, speed-ease-affordability, and special facilities and treatment for vulnerable groups (Sukorina, 2025). Within this mechanism, tangibles refer to the physical aspects of service, such as facilities, equipment, staff appearance, and other supporting infrastructure visible and perceptible to users. Although some basic facilities are available and partially meet the needs of vulnerable groups, there remain significant gaps preventing the achievement of these standards. Services are not consistently delivered on time, causing delays in administrative processes for persons with disabilities, the elderly, and pregnant women—violating the “timeliness” aspect. Furthermore, the absence of communication aids, the lack of private consultation rooms, and limited disability-friendly transportation reduce the speed, ease, and affordability of services. These inadequacies impose additional burdens on vulnerable groups, both in time and financial cost.

The lack of special facilities also contradicts the principle of providing “special facilities and treatment for vulnerable groups,” which aims to ensure fairness in service delivery. To align DPMPTSP practices with the standards outlined by Zeitham (2009), concrete steps must include providing communication aids—such as hearing support systems and sign language interpreters—establishing private consultation rooms, and ensuring inclusive transportation services or partnerships with accessible public transport providers. By integrating these three dimensions, DPMPTSP Balikpapan can improve user satisfaction and realize inclusive, responsive, and equitable public services, particularly for vulnerable groups.

This mechanism aligns with prior research by Rio Winanta (2022), who emphasized that public services for persons with disabilities must be supported by adequate facilities to ensure optimal service delivery.

2. Responsiveness

Responsiveness emphasizes the willingness and ability of officers to provide assistance and respond to users' needs or complaints quickly and appropriately. DPMPTSP Balikpapan, as the institution responsible for licensing and integrated services, has provided generally good services but still faces challenges in delivering optimal services, especially for vulnerable groups. This highlights the need for improved specialized service mechanisms to ensure more responsive and inclusive delivery.

According to Masiroh (2024), many members of vulnerable groups have physical or mental limitations that restrict their ability to fully participate in social life. These limitations make special treatment essential in public services. Without mechanisms tailored to their needs, vulnerable groups cannot access services equitably or with dignity. Examples include accessible facilities for persons with disabilities, assistance services for individuals with mental limitations, or technologies that facilitate online access. Such measures are crucial to ensure vulnerable groups receive public services equally and without discrimination. Therefore, public services must be designed and implemented with careful consideration of the specific needs of vulnerable groups, including disability-friendly access, easy-to-understand communication, and adequate psychological support. This approach not only improves service quality but also ensures inclusivity and social justice (Rafah et al., 2025). Thus, services responsive to the physical and mental limitations of vulnerable groups can form the foundation for truly inclusive and equitable public service delivery. This mechanism supports earlier findings by Salman Dumana, who emphasized that the challenges faced by vulnerable groups in public services must be matched by fulfilling their needs.

3. Reliability

Reliability in public service mechanisms is a crucial aspect reflecting the quality and consistency of services provided to the public, particularly vulnerable groups such as persons with disabilities. At DPMPTSP Balikpapan, reliability is evident in the well-structured service procedures implemented in accordance with field data obtained from surveys. Services for applicants with disabilities at DPMPTSP Balikpapan are designed with structured steps to ensure accessibility and adequate assistance. The procedure begins with providing designated parking spaces for persons with disabilities, demonstrating initial attention to their physical needs. Next, reception staff provide a special identification badge, which helps streamline administrative processes and prevent unnecessary bureaucratic barriers. Additional convenience is provided through priority queues and special seating, enhancing comfort and reducing physical strain while waiting. This shows that the service prioritizes not just formal procedures but also the humane needs and comfort of service users. The next step involves direct service at a special counter equipped with sign language interpreter support, including the option for consultation via video call. This is crucial for bridging communication with applicants who have hearing or speech impairments, ensuring that the service process is effective and inclusive. The use of technologies such as video calls and WhatsApp further demonstrates DPMPTSP's adaptation to digital innovation for expanding access and flexibility. Finally, document collection or delivery through GoSend (Gojek) provides additional reliability for applicants who may have mobility difficulties. This shows the institution's commitment to providing responsive, adaptive services tailored to the specific needs of vulnerable groups.

Overall, the service mechanism at DPMPTSP Balikpapan reflects high reliability through well-implemented procedures focused on accessibility, comfort, and effective communication for applicants with disabilities. This approach not only fulfills public service standards but also reinforces principles of inclusivity and social justice. From the perspective of efficiency theory in public service, which states that service requirements must be limited only to elements directly related to achieving service objectives and must consider the integration between requirements and service outputs (Kesuma, 2021), DPMPTSP Balikpapan has met these principles. By avoiding duplicate or unnecessary requirements and integrating various support services within one coordinated system, DPMPTSP successfully creates an efficient, focused service process. Efficiency is also reflected in the use of digital technologies to facilitate communication and document delivery, reducing waiting time and administrative burden for applicants with disabilities. This approach enhances service quality and minimizes resource and time waste—core principles of public service efficiency.

Thus, the reliability of DPMPTSP Balikpapan's service mechanism is demonstrated not only through accurate and systematic procedures but also through the application of efficiency principles that ensure optimal, integrated, and responsive services for vulnerable groups. Special services provided to persons with disabilities at DPMPTSP Balikpapan have resulted in a high level of satisfaction among service users. This indicates that the facilities and procedures designed to meet the needs of vulnerable groups have been effective and have met their expectations. However, even with high satisfaction, it remains essential to maintain a continuous focus on improving service quality so that mechanisms remain optimal and able to adapt to changes in community needs. Public service itself is a governmental obligation in fulfilling citizens' rights, including the right to fair and non-discriminatory access to services. In this regard, the modern public service theory by Scupola & Mergel (2022) is highly relevant. They view public service as a comprehensive and integrated system that involves not only the government but also active public participation in value co-creation.

This concept highlights the importance of interactive relationships between service providers and users. Through effective interaction, service providers gain deeper understanding of community needs and expectations, allowing them to design and implement more targeted services that prioritize user satisfaction. This mechanism aligns with findings by Suyani, which emphasized that service programs operate effectively when there is synergy among various actors to ensure precise and targeted implementation. Furthermore, the theory stresses the need for a professional and adaptive bureaucratic reform. Such reform aims to build a bureaucracy capable of responding to social and technological developments, enhancing transparency, and strengthening accountability in service delivery. With professional and adaptive bureaucracy, specialized services for vulnerable groups, such as persons with disabilities, can continue to develop innovatively and sustainably. Thus, the satisfaction achieved by applicants with disabilities at DPMPTSP Balikpapan is the result of synergy between structured service delivery, interactive communication with users, and a responsive bureaucracy. To maintain and enhance this quality, ongoing commitment to bureaucratic reform that upholds professionalism and adaptability is essential. Therefore, comprehensive and integrated public service, as conceptualized by Scupola & Mergel, serves as an important foundation for building an inclusive, effective, and sustainable service system—especially in serving vulnerable groups such as persons with disabilities.

4) Assurance

The issue of staff competence is a crucial factor that influences the quantity of services that can be delivered, both online and offline, at the DPMPTSP of Balikpapan City. Data show that the realization of service targets, particularly online services, is still relatively low. This may be attributed to the suboptimal skills and technical abilities of staff in managing and operating digital service systems. The competence or skills of staff in performing their duties greatly determine the quality and quantity of services provided. Staff with high competence are able to deliver services according to established standards quickly, accurately, and efficiently. Conversely, if staff competence is inadequate, service processes may be hampered, resulting in slow, suboptimal service delivery, and consequently, low achievement of service targets. In the context of online services, the IT expert group at DPMPTSP needs to receive specialized training to improve their ability to operate digital platforms and provide services that are easily accessible to the public. This training must include technical aspects such as application management, data security, and effective digital communication so that online services can run smoothly and provide convenience to users.

According to competency theory in public service, technical capabilities and professionalism of staff are among the main pillars required to ensure services meet expected standards. This competence includes not only technical knowledge and skills but also attitudes and the ability to adapt to technological changes and community needs. By improving staff competence through continuous training and professional development, DPMPTSP Balikpapan City can enhance both the quantity and quality of services, especially in optimizing online services, which are currently still underutilized. This will help create services that are fast, accurate, and responsive to public needs, enabling service targets to be achieved more effectively. Continuous training and development are key to ensuring that public services can operate more optimally and remain accessible to the public. In this era of digitalization—particularly regarding online and offline services at DPMPTSP Balikpapan—enhancing staff competence is crucial so they can operate the systems and technologies effectively. According to Pratiwi et al. (2022), ongoing training not only improves technical skills but also builds the professional and adaptive attitudes needed to meet the increasingly complex demands of society. With structured and continuous training programs, staff can update their knowledge and master emerging technologies, making service processes faster, more accurate, and more responsive. This greatly affects the quality and quantity of services provided, ensuring that the public receives services that meet standards while also offering accessibility and satisfaction. Therefore, investing in staff training and development at DPMPTSP Balikpapan City must be a strategic priority so that public services can continue to improve and adapt to changing times.

4. Empathy

Empathy emphasizes providing personal attention to customers by understanding their specific needs individually so they feel valued and personally attended to. The implementation of empathy in services at DPMPTSP Balikpapan City has become a key focus, particularly in supporting vulnerable groups so they can access public services comfortably and with dignity. Through staff awareness-building and guidance on the importance of empathy, vulnerable groups feel respected and acknowledged, which directly enhances their comfort and trust when using public services. This is highly important since many members of vulnerable groups have physical or mental limitations that restrict their ability to participate fully in society (Masiroh, 2024). These limitations require special treatment in public services to ensure equitable and non-discriminatory access, aligning with the

principles of social justice (Salman, 2020). Moreover, vulnerable groups often face discrimination based on factors such as age, gender, economic status, ethnicity, or health conditions, leading to their exclusion from the general public. Such discrimination and marginalization not only hinder their participation in social and economic life but also increase the risk of injustice and inequality in accessing public services (Riswandie, 2023). Therefore, the application of empathy by service staff is crucial in reducing these barriers and ensuring more humane, inclusive treatment. Empathy in public services not only improves the quality of interactions between service providers and users but also serves as a foundation for developing policies and procedures that are responsive to the specific needs of vulnerable groups. Thus, DPMPTSP Balikpapan City can create an inclusive and welcoming service environment that guarantees equal rights and legal protection for vulnerable individuals. This also helps build public trust and strengthens the legitimacy of public services as a right for all citizens without exception. Providing personal attention to vulnerable groups in public services is a strategic step in creating a meaningful and inclusive service experience. In the context of DPMPTSP Balikpapan City, understanding the unique needs of each individual within vulnerable groups enables service officers to deliver more tailored and sensitive treatment. This personalized approach not only makes vulnerable individuals feel valued but also increases their confidence and comfort in accessing public services. By recognizing differing needs—whether physical, mental, or socio-economic—staff can adjust service processes to meet not only procedural standards but also essential humanitarian aspects. This personal attention demonstrates that public services at DPMPTSP are not merely administrative but oriented toward empowerment and respect for human dignity, especially for vulnerable individuals. This approach aligns with humanistic and inclusive service principles, emphasizing that every individual is entitled to fair services that acknowledge their unique conditions and needs. Ultimately, such personalized attention greatly contributes to building public trust and loyalty as well as strengthening the institution's legitimacy as a responsive and caring public service provider.

Based on the fulfilled indicators for public service implementation for vulnerable groups proposed by Zanthem, the specifications provided are still insufficient. In this study, the researcher identifies a gap in existing literature that has yet to address the provision of services for vulnerable groups, particularly in relation to inclusive design. This mechanism explains the importance of ease, independence, comfort, and safety. These indicators can be created and proposed by the researcher considering individual issues that must be accommodated. The mechanism must emphasize a design process that directly involves the voices of vulnerable groups. Therefore, new regulations issued may refer to the Regulation of the Minister of State Apparatus Empowerment and Bureaucratic Reform (Permen PANRB) Number 11 of 2024 concerning the Implementation of Public Services Friendly to Vulnerable Groups. This regulation serves as an important legal foundation that strengthens the government's commitment to ensuring inclusive and equitable public services in Indonesia. It was issued in response to the urgent need to implement the principles of equality and non-discrimination mandated by Law Number 25 of 2009 on Public Services in a more specific manner. Its primary objectives are to realize inclusive public services, protect and fulfill the rights of vulnerable groups, improve service quality according to their needs, and eliminate all forms of discrimination. To achieve these goals, the regulation emphasizes accessibility in physical facilities and information, equal treatment, non-discrimination, and sensitivity among service staff. The implications for public service organizers include improving accessible facilities and infrastructure, enhancing human resource capacity through inclusive communication training, adapting service standards to integrate special needs, and formulating internal policies that support the implementation of this regulation. Thus, Permen PANRB Number 11 of 2024 is expected to increase public trust, encourage active participation of vulnerable groups, build a positive government image, and ultimately uphold social justice for all citizens.

Factors Influencing the Provision of Public Services for Vulnerable Groups at DPMPTSP Balikpapan City

Various factors influencing public services for vulnerable groups at DPMPTSP Balikpapan City refer to Moenir's theory, including the following:

1. Awareness Factor

The awareness factor serves as the main foundation for improving the quality of public services, especially for vulnerable groups at DPMPTSP Balikpapan City. High awareness among service providers and the community regarding the importance of delivering inclusive and responsive services to vulnerable groups will encourage the creation of more effective, just, and respectful public services. The theory of awareness in public service emphasizes that when service providers possess a strong understanding of the urgency of inclusive service delivery, their commitment to providing optimal service will increase significantly. This awareness includes understanding the rights of vulnerable groups, the challenges they face, and the importance of applying principles

of social justice in all aspects of service provision. In addition, public awareness as service users also plays a crucial role in creating a supportive service environment. Communities that understand the rights and needs of vulnerable groups tend to support inclusive policies and participate in maintaining service quality. Therefore, increasing awareness must be carried out continuously through education, training, socialization, and campaigns involving all stakeholders. This approach aligns with the theory that collective awareness is key to building a service culture oriented toward satisfaction and protection of vulnerable groups. Improving awareness enables DPMPTSP Balikpapan City to strengthen its institutional capacity and human resources, so that the services delivered not only meet technical standards but also consider humanitarian and equality aspects. Ultimately, this will enhance public trust and reinforce the legitimacy of the government as an inclusive and just service provider. Enhancing awareness among service providers and the public—especially vulnerable groups—is a crucial factor in supporting inclusive and responsive public services (Rifai & Anadza, 2025). High awareness among service providers helps create a work environment that is more sensitive to the special needs of vulnerable communities, ensuring that the services provided do not merely meet procedural standards but also uphold humanity and social justice. Meanwhile, awareness among vulnerable groups enables them to access services more actively and communicate their needs and rights effectively. Although significant progress has been made through training and socialization conducted by DPMPTSP Balikpapan City, efforts to strengthen awareness must continue to be sustained to internalize values of inclusion and empathy within the public service culture. Continuous education and communication are essential to developing public services that are more effective, empathetic, and adaptive to changing community needs. Thus, awareness-building not only strengthens the commitment of service providers but also increases public trust and participation, particularly among vulnerable groups, in ensuring dignified and equitable public services.

2. Regulatory Factor

Quality and inclusive public services heavily depend on the presence of clear regulations, policies, and standards as guidelines for service implementation (Kesuma, 2021). Regulations outline procedures, rights, obligations, and sanctions in case of violations, thereby creating order in public service operations. At the Investment and One-Stop Integrated Services Office (DPMPTSP) of Balikpapan City, various national and local regulations serve as the legal and technical basis for service delivery, especially for vulnerable groups such as persons with disabilities. These regulations function not only as administrative controls but also as instruments to ensure that services meet the principles of accessibility, justice, and the protection of vulnerable groups' rights. With clear legal and technical guidelines as operational foundations, DPMPTSP Balikpapan City is expected to deliver services that go beyond formal administrative requirements by emphasizing humanitarian and social justice aspects. Although regulations provide consistency and accountability, without attention to the specific needs of vulnerable groups, service quality will fall short of inclusivity goals. Thus, such guidelines must be translated into responsive and empathetic service practices, where officers understand and respect differences in individual needs—particularly among persons with disabilities, the elderly, and other vulnerable groups. This approach enhances accessibility, comfort, and public trust in service delivery. Ultimately, it demonstrates the government's commitment to achieving social justice and equal opportunities for all citizens. These findings align with Rio Winanta's research, which highlights the importance of structured regulations as a protective legal umbrella for vulnerable groups in accessing public services.

3. Organizational Factor

Effective and inclusive public services for vulnerable groups at DPMPTSP Balikpapan City are strongly influenced by internal organizational factors, including organizational structure, work culture, coordination, and leadership. A well-defined and organized structure serves as the foundation for ensuring that every organizational function operates effectively. A clear structure enables better task distribution and responsibility, ensuring that services for vulnerable groups can be provided with focused attention. In the context of DPMPTSP Balikpapan City, having a specialized unit dedicated to handling vulnerable groups is essential. Such a unit concentrates expertise and resources to deliver more responsive services tailored to specific needs. It also facilitates monitoring, evaluation, and timely problem-solving. Beyond structure, an inclusive work culture is equally important. A culture that embraces empathy, professionalism, and collaboration motivates employees to serve wholeheartedly. This aligns with the findings of Ahmad Salman, who emphasized that vulnerable groups must receive special attention in public service delivery. Coordination among organizational units is another crucial factor. According to Lawrence and Lorsch's theory of coordination, effective coordination helps overcome task complexity and functional differences, ensuring harmonious and efficient service delivery. In DPMPTSP, good coordination allows units to complement each other in serving vulnerable groups promptly and effectively.

Visionary and inclusive leadership also plays a decisive role. Leaders at DPMPTSP must inspire and motivate their staff to prioritize quality and inclusivity in public services. Transformational leadership, as explained by Bass, drives organizational commitment to achieving inclusive and high-quality service delivery. Leaders who are proactive and responsive to societal needs—especially those of vulnerable groups—can foster an adaptive and solution-oriented work environment.

4. Income Factor

The availability of budget or institutional revenue determines the ability to provide facilities, infrastructure, and human resources to support the service delivery process. The availability of an institution's budget or revenue is one of the key factors that significantly influences its capacity to deliver adequate and quality public services. At the Balikpapan City DPMPTSP, a sufficient budget not only enables the implementation of various service programs and activities but also ensures that the necessary resources are available in sufficient quantity and quality to optimally serve vulnerable groups. Without adequate budget support, efforts to improve service quality may be hindered, and even the quantity of services provided may become limited. Theoretically, according to the public financial management approach, effective and efficient budget allocation serves as the foundation for achieving inclusive and equitable public service goals (Lathifah et al., 2024). A sufficient budget enables funding for staff training, the development of service information systems, and the implementation of special programs targeting the needs of vulnerable groups. On the other hand, budget limitations often force service priorities to focus on administrative aspects, resulting in insufficient attention to humanitarian aspects and the special needs of vulnerable groups.

In addition, stable institutional income is necessary to maintain service continuity. When the budget fluctuates or becomes insufficient, public services may experience disruptions such as process delays, declining facility quality, or even discontinuation of essential services. This has a negative impact on public perception, especially among vulnerable groups who depend heavily on these services. At the Balikpapan City DPMPTSP, transparent and accountable budget management is key to ensuring that the available funds are optimally used to provide inclusive public services. Performance-based budgeting can be applied to ensure that every expenditure directly contributes to improving service quality and quantity for vulnerable groups. Adequate budget availability and sound financial management form an important foundation for realizing responsive, high-quality, and equitable public services at the Balikpapan City DPMPTSP. This strengthens public trust—particularly among vulnerable groups—in the local government as a service provider that is attentive and capable of meeting their needs sustainably.

The budget plays not only a role in providing physical facilities and services but is also crucial in supporting training and skill development for staff who directly interact with vulnerable communities. Training focused on inclusive service delivery, effective communication, and a deep understanding of the specific needs of vulnerable groups will enhance the quality of interaction and responsiveness of staff in facing various situations. With adequate budgeting, the Balikpapan City DPMPTSP can organize structured and continuous training programs, including workshops, seminars, interpersonal skills training, and empathy-based service simulations. According to human resource development theory, investment in staff training is an effective way to strengthen organizational capacity in delivering responsive and equitable services (Fitriatun et al., 2025). Staff with strong competencies in understanding the characteristics and needs of vulnerable groups will be able to provide more personal, empathetic, and solution-oriented services, creating a positive service experience. This aligns with the principles of public service that place humans at the center of attention, not merely administrative procedures. This mechanism also supports previous research by Rio Winanta, which emphasizes that the rights of persons with disabilities to public services must be supported by adequate resources.

Additionally, training funded by the institution's budget helps build an inclusive and professional work culture within the DPMPTSP. Staff who continuously develop their competencies will be more motivated and better prepared to face the dynamic challenges of public service, particularly in responding to the diverse needs of vulnerable communities. Thus, budget allocation for staff competency development is a strategic investment that directly contributes to improving the quality of public services. Practically, the budget allocated for training may cover expert speaker fees, training materials, supporting technologies such as e-learning platforms, and monitoring and evaluation of training effectiveness. These components ensure that training is not merely a formality but truly enhances staff competencies in delivering inclusive and responsive services.

5. Task Skill Factor

The task skill factor or staff competence plays a central role in ensuring the quality of public services delivered to vulnerable groups at the Balikpapan City DPMPTSP. This competence includes not only the technical abilities

required to execute administrative and service procedures but also comprehensive knowledge of service regulations and essential interpersonal skills for effective and empathetic communication with individuals who have diverse needs, especially vulnerable groups. According to competency theory in human resource management, competence is a combination of knowledge, skills, and attitudes that individuals must possess to perform tasks effectively and efficiently (Netaniel Giovanni & Ali, 2024). In the context of public service delivery, staff competence is crucial to ensure that services provided not only meet established standards but also respond to the special needs of vulnerable groups quickly and appropriately. This is key to preventing service errors, delays, or discrimination that could disadvantage the public.

Technical competencies include mastery of administrative procedures, the use of service information technology, and understanding of applicable policies and regulations. Meanwhile, interpersonal skills—such as effective communication, patience, empathy, and the ability to handle complex situations—are essential for staff to understand and meet the needs of vulnerable groups in a friendly and inclusive manner. The development of staff competence must also be prioritized as part of the strategy to enhance public service quality. Continuous training and professional development programs can strengthen both technical and interpersonal abilities so that staff are always prepared to face dynamic service challenges. With adequate competence, staff can deliver fast, accurate, and standardized services while building public trust in government institutions.

Task skills or staff competencies serve as the foundation for ensuring effective and efficient inclusive public services at the Balikpapan City DPMPTSP. Investment in developing these competencies directly contributes to improving public satisfaction and well-being—particularly for vulnerable groups who require special attention in accessing public services. This mechanism supports previous research by Suyani, which emphasizes that competence supported by staff abilities enables optimal service delivery. It also aligns with findings from Ahmad Salman, who highlights the urgency of competence in fulfilling the rights of vulnerable groups in accessing public services.

6. Facility Factor

The facility factor is a highly crucial aspect in determining the success of public service delivery, particularly for vulnerable groups at the Balikpapan City DPMPTSP. Facilities include various physical and non-physical elements such as building amenities, information technology equipment, operational vehicles, and other supporting infrastructure that directly influence the smoothness and quality of service delivery. The availability and adequacy of facilities enable service processes to run smoothly, quickly, and effectively, ensuring that the needs of vulnerable groups are optimally met. Facilities serve as one of the essential resources supporting operational effectiveness and efficiency. Complete and standardized facilities not only improve employee productivity in delivering services but also enhance public satisfaction and trust, especially among vulnerable groups who require special attention. Conversely, insufficient facilities can hinder service processes, create discomfort, and even lead to indirect discrimination against groups requiring inclusive services.

The absence of special facilities for individuals with disabilities at the Balikpapan City DPMPTSP—such as dedicated service counters, disability-friendly waiting rooms, accessible guiding blocks, assistive tools for the visually and hearing impaired, inclusive children's play areas, special toilets, elevators with Braille buttons, and mobility aids—indicates significant shortcomings in public service infrastructure. This condition highlights the need for improvements and adjustments to physical facilities so that services can be delivered inclusively, equitably, and in accordance with laws and regulations governing the rights of persons with disabilities. According to facility management theory in the context of public services, physical facilities include buildings, information technology equipment, operational vehicles, and other supporting infrastructure that directly affect the smoothness and quality of service delivery. Adequate facilities not only ensure easier access and comfort for service users but also reflect the institution's commitment to implementing the principles of social justice and inclusivity. When physical facilities do not meet accessibility standards, persons with disabilities face significant barriers in accessing public services, which in turn reduces the effectiveness and efficiency of the service itself. This contradicts the principles of public service that are responsive and attentive to the diverse needs of the community. Therefore, integrating accessibility aspects in the development of physical facilities is essential to ensure that all citizens, including persons with disabilities, can receive equitable and dignified services. The development of inclusive physical facilities must be supported by proper planning, sufficient budget allocation, and the involvement of relevant stakeholders, including disability communities, to ensure that their needs are adequately met. This aligns with both international and national standards on accessibility in public services, as stipulated in the Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (CRPD) and related government regulations.

Thus, improving disability-friendly infrastructure at the Balikpapan City DPMPTSP is not merely a matter of fulfilling administrative requirements but is a real manifestation of the local government's commitment to creating inclusive, equitable, and high-quality public services for all members of society. This mechanism supports previous research by Suyani Ewi, which emphasizes that programs can operate effectively only when supported by adequate facilities.

CONCLUSION

1. The quality of public services for vulnerable groups at the Balikpapan City DPMPTSP emphasizes: Tangibles. Public services for vulnerable groups at the Balikpapan City DPMPTSP have provided several essential facilities such as physical accessibility (ramps, elevators, and disability-friendly toilets), priority queue lanes, and assistance services. However, there are still significant shortcomings in supporting facilities such as communication aids, consultation rooms that ensure confidentiality, and special transportation facilities. These shortcomings remain a major challenge in achieving services that are truly inclusive and responsive. Responsiveness. The service mechanisms show good performance, with average public satisfaction ratings falling into the “Good” to “Very Good” categories. Officers are considered friendly and responsive; however, there are weaknesses in complaint handling and specialized assistance services for vulnerable groups. As a result, services have not fully reached optimal and consistent performance in meeting the specific needs of these groups. Reliability. The service procedures implemented are already appropriate and have received “Very Good” ratings from the public. This indicates that services are carried out correctly and in accordance with established standards. However, the effectiveness of these procedures must be continuously maintained and improved to ensure that services remain reliable and trustworthy for vulnerable groups.
2. Factors influencing public services for vulnerable groups at the Balikpapan City DPMPTSP include awareness, regulations, organization, and income. High awareness among service providers and the community forms the main foundation for creating inclusive services that respond to the needs of vulnerable groups. The existence of clear regulations, policies, and standards provides strong legal and technical guidelines to ensure equitable and high-quality service delivery. An appropriate organizational structure, an inclusive work culture, effective inter-departmental coordination, and visionary and supportive leadership are internal factors that strongly determine service success. The availability of sufficient budget or institutional income is also a crucial factor influencing the ability to provide adequate facilities, infrastructure, and human resources necessary to support optimal public service delivery. Overall, synergy among these factors is essential to ensuring effective, inclusive, and equitable public services for vulnerable groups at the Balikpapan City DPMPTSP. Therefore, efforts to increase awareness, strengthen regulations, improve organizational structure and culture, and enhance sound financial management must be carried out continuously to improve the quality of public services provided.

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